

African American Burial Grounds in the Louisiana River Parishes

Brendan Harmon · Nicholas Serrano · Annicia Streete

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Summary

This project aims to document African American burial grounds in the Louisiana River Parishes. The Louisiana River Parishes are scattered with hundreds of African American cemeteries dating back to the antebellum period when plantations lined both sides of the Mississippi River. This history of environmental racism continued into the 20th century as the region was favored for hazardous petrochemical production facilities. Today these cultural landscapes are threatened by industrial expansion, climate change, missing land-tenure records, and dwindling populations of descendant communities. Our team 3D scanned burial grounds and compiled a database of interactive, publicly accessible digital models to preserve the record of these cultural landscapes. The project leads are Annicia Streete, Brendan Harmon, and Nicholas Serrano. This research was funded by grants from the National Park Service's National Center for Preservation Technology and Training, the Architecture Research Centers Consortium, and Louisiana State University. This project was supported by the LSU Center for GeoInformatics and the LSU Coastal Ecosystem Design Studio. The dataset was released under the Creative Commons Zero public domain dedication.

Citing

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Methods	3
2.1	Lidar	3
2.2	Soundscapes	4
2.3	Neural rendering	4
2.4	Point clouds	5
2.5	Digital fabrication	6
3	Burial Grounds	10
3.1	Alford	12
3.2	Alma	16
3.3	Ashland	18
3.4	Chamberlin	20
3.5	Lady of Knight	22
3.6	Mulatto Bend	24
3.7	Orange Grove	26
3.8	Mt. Zion Riverlake	28
3.9	Silvery	30
3.10	St. Catherine	32
3.11	United Benevolent Society	34
4	Dataset	35
5	Papers	35
6	Presentations	35
7	Poster	36
8	Exhibitions	36
9	Acknowledgements	36

1 Introduction

Figure 1: Mt. Zion Riverlake Cemetery, Pointe Coupee Parish, Louisiana, 2024

The burial grounds of enslaved African Americans and their descendants are an invaluable, but weakly preserved part of our cultural heritage (Figures 1–3). In southern Louisiana, these burial grounds are typically clusters of concrete box graves or stone markers under a relict stand of old growth, heritage trees. Many of these sites on former plantations are undocumented, inaccessible, untended, or at risk of development. The cemeteries that remain are important cultural landscapes that make up a vital part of this region’s historical geography.

Traditional methods of historic preservation documentation in the United States developed out of, and adopted the techniques of, architectural practice using line drawings to record buildings. Landscapes, however, are infamously difficult to accurately represent in line drawings, and their character depends on experiential qualities of time and space. Cemeteries are even more complicated because they are not a singular object, but a composition of multiple elements that together with practices and rituals inform the cultural significance of the site. The character and context of these landscapes are essential parts of their stories.

Landscapes are complex sites rich with cultural artifacts important to the humanities and can serve as a nexus for organizing our understanding of human relationships to nature and one another. Traditional analog methods of preservation documentation are wholly inadequate for recording such complex sites. Close-range remote sensing techniques such as airborne lidar, terrestrial laser scanning, and photogrammetric reconstruction can be used to document landscapes in more of their messy complexity. In recent years, point clouds – sets of spatial coordinates – from close-range remote sensing have emerged as a new medium for representing precisely landscape in its complexity [1]. Despite recent advances, however, it is still challenging to reconstruct landscapes using close-range remote sensing.

The aim of this project was to record extant burial grounds of enslaved African Americans and their descendants in the River Parishes of Louisiana. We rapidly surveyed eleven cemeteries in West Baton Rouge and Pointe Coupee parishes and documented one – Alford Cemetery – extensively with detailed reconstructions of every tomb. To do so, we developed a process for documenting these landscapes’ spatial and aural character in high fidelity, immersive detail using close-range remote sensing, neural rendering, and spatial audio. When possible, we used open source software and open data formats for the sake of transparency, reproducibility, interoperability, and longevity. Our models can be viewed online as interactive point cloud visualizations at <https://xyz.cct.lsu.edu> and our dataset is archived online on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17613647> under the Creative Commons Zero license.

Figure 2: Detail with Alford and Chamberlin. United States Geological Survey, 1906, Bayou Sara Quadrangle, Louisiana. Scale: 1:125000.

Figure 3: Detail with Mulatto Bend Benevolent Society Cemetery. United States Geological Survey, 1954, Scotlandville Quadrangle, Louisiana. 7.5 Minute Series.

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2 Methods

Heritage sites around the world are being scanned to document their cultural heritage. While buildings and artifacts can be scanned effectively using close-range remote sensing, cultural landscapes are challenging to reconstruct due to their scale, complexity, and dynamism. While an uncrewed aerial system – a drone in common parlance – with lidar or imaging systems can rapidly capture a landscape from above, much of the landscape is likely to be occluded by plants, resulting in an incomplete reconstruction. Terrestrial laser scanners can capture some of what airborne sensors cannot, such as the understory of trees or the details of burial markers. Surveys with terrestrial laser scanners, however, are time consuming, logistically challenging, and can prove prohibitively expensive. Detailed reconstructions typically require dense sampling, especially in landscapes with dense vegetation or complex terrain, increasing the time, cost, and logistics of fieldwork. Close-range remote sensing techniques are sensitive to environmental factors such as wind, weather, and illumination which can cause noise and yield incomplete reconstructions. Emerging techniques for neural rendering [8, 4], however, can be used to rapidly reconstruct landscapes in high fidelity.

Most of the African American burial grounds in the River Parishes of Louisiana have been lost and those that remain are endangered. To document the spatial and aural character of cultural landscapes before they disappear, we collected lidar, soundscapes, and neural renderings. We used drone lidar to rapidly scan eleven cemeteries. We recorded ambisonic sound fields for eight cemeteries. We used neural renderings to record the tombs and burial markers for one site – Alford Cemetery in West Baton Rouge Parish – in high fidelity. These scans captured details including inscriptions, artificial flowers, the texture of concrete, lichen, and coats of peeling paint. We also experimented with 3D printing to create material artifacts for exhibitions that would also serve as physical archives of our scans.

2.1 Lidar

We used a drone with lidar to rapidly survey eleven cemeteries at centimeter point sampling density so that we could preserve a record of the spatial conditions of these endangered landscapes (Figures 9, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21, 23, 25, 26, 27, & 28). To survey the sites, we used a quadcopter with a real-time kinematic global navigation satellite system and a lidar sensor (Figure 4). With drone lidar, we were able to map inaccessible sites such as Chamberlin Cemetery that cannot legally be reached on foot. All of the sites were occluded by vegetation and many – including Ashland, Chamberlin, St. Catherine, and Silvery Cemeteries – were completely overgrown. Because of the dense vegetation engulfing many of the cemeteries, we were not able to record all of the extant tombs and burial markers. Given the speed and altitude of the drone and the sampling rate of the sensor, we were able to capture the shape, but not the details of unoccluded tombs. While these aerial surveys captured only an incomplete record of the cemeteries, they document the cemeteries in context. They record the corduroy texture of the canefields (Figures 9, 13, 15, 17, 21, 23, 25, 26, & 27), the earthworking and industrial operations (Figure 21), and the blue tarp clad roofs of storm-battered communities (Figure 19 & 28) that surround the cemeteries. The surveys also demonstrate some of the risks, such as windthrow, that these cemeteries face. We flew over Alford Cemetery, for example, shortly after a storm to document the fallen trees and shattered vaults (Figure 9).

Figure 4: DJI Matrice 300 RTK L1 Lidar

2.2 Soundscapes

To document the aural character of these cultural landscapes, we recorded spatial audio at eight of the burial grounds. We collected ambisonic recordings which capture a sound field, a sphere of sound ideal for immersive audio experiences such as virtual reality. This format encodes the direction, distance, and elevation of sound waves captured by an array of microphones. Soundscapes reproduced with ambisonics localize sound, recreating a realistic experience of hearing sounds from all directions [21]. Soundscapes can be visualized as spectrograms which show how frequency spectra evolve over time (Figures 10, 14, 16, 18, 20, 22, 24, & 29).

2.3 Neural rendering

Neural rendering techniques can be used to rapidly reconstruct challenging scenes such as landscapes in precise, immersive detail with only a camera (Figure 5). We used two neural renderings techniques –neural radiance fields and 3D Gaussian splatting – to reconstruct tombs and burial markers in high fidelity. Both of these are machine learning techniques for novel view synthesis – for generating unseen views from an existing collection of views of a scene. These techniques can be used to reconstruct scenes in 3D from a sparse collection of images. A neural radiance field is a five dimensional function that represents a scene as a continuous volumetric field with variable density and emitted radiance [8]. The function is ap-

proximated and then optimized by a neural network trained on a set of images. It is rendered by casting camera rays through the field and optimized by minimizing the difference between the rendered views and original images. While radiance fields were originally intended for rendering images or videos, they can also be exported as point clouds. 3D Gaussian splats can be trained faster and rendered in real-time [4]. With this technique, a scene is represented discretely as 3D volumetric Gaussians – sets of mean spatial coordinates, anisotropic covariance, opacity, and spherical harmonics – rather than a continuous field. Since this data structure can be rasterized efficiently with tile based splatting, it can be rendered at high resolution in real-time. While neural radiance fields can generate higher fidelity reconstructions, Gaussian splatting allows for real-time rendering. Therefore, we used neural radiance fields to reconstruct scenes for point cloud modeling and visualization (Figure 6), while we used 3D Gaussian splatting to create immersive, interactive, online experiences (Figure 7).

To reconstruct tombs with neural rendering, we first captured imagery of tombs, then trained our neural renderings, and finally exported the results. We collected imagery in the field, taking a spiral of photos or video around each tomb. When tombs were tightly clustered, we captured them as an ensemble. At Alford Cemetery, we reconstructed 35 individual tombs and 16 ensembles. Then we used nerfstudio, a free and open source library for neural radiance fields [5], to process the imagery using structure from motion and multi-view stereo [12, 13], train the Nerfacto and Splatfacto models, and export the results (Figure 6). We used three metrics – peak signal-to-noise ratio, structural similarity index measure [19], and learned perceptual image patch similarity [10] – to quantitatively evaluate the quality of our reconstructions.

Figure 5: Neural rendering

2.4 Point clouds

We used neural renderings to create high fidelity reconstructions of tombs and burial markers for point cloud processing. These reconstructions captured details including inscriptions, decorations, and textures, but were marred by noise because they were captured in the wild with dynamic environmental conditions, so we used point cloud processing in CCloudCompare [18] to isolate, clean, and color balance the tombs. First, dense point clouds with approximately 2 million points were sampled from the neural renderings using ray marching. We isolated individual tombs by manually segmenting the point clouds. Then we cleaned the point clouds using noise and statistical outlier removal algorithms, before manually segmented out any remaining noise. White points were removed with colorimetric segmentation and then each point cloud was color balanced. The point clouds were saved in common open formats including plain text ply format and binary e57 [16], laz [15, 11], and pcd formats [17].

The point clouds can be interactively viewed online using the Potree render engine (Schuetz 2015, Schuetz 2020) on our server xyz.cct.lsu.edu (Figure 11). While the neural renderings approach photorealism, the point clouds, which we render as splats illuminated by eye-dome lighting, are a more abstract medium with a pointillistic aesthetic [6] (Figure 7).

Figure 6: Rendering a neural radiance field in nerfstudio

2.5 Digital fabrication

As computational media, point clouds and neural renderings can represent heritage landscapes in high fidelity and can be shared online to reach a wide audience, but lack material presence. We use 3D printing to rematerialize these immaterial virtual artifacts, restoring physical form and material presence to our digital archive. These 3D printed artifacts are tactile, occupy space, have mass and texture, and interact with light. While computational media can reach a wide audience online, these 3D printed artifacts are an accessible, evocative medium for exhibitions in physical spaces such as galleries and museums.

We use a volumetric modeling process to prepare point clouds for 3D printing [2]. While point clouds are simply a set of positional coordinates without form or volume, they can be modeled volumetrically as voxels, as 3D cells in a 3D raster grid. Point clouds are voxelized by sampling each cell of the grid to check whether any points are present. Cells containing points become cuboids, while cells without points remain voids. The detail of the resulting volumetric model depends upon the resolution of the 3D grid. Higher resolution grids preserve more spatial data, but too fine a grid will not fill the space between points. While lower resolution grids can effectively fill the space between points, when a grid is too coarse it looks blocky and loses important details. The marching cubes algorithm [20], however, can be used to model a

smoother, but still angular mesh from the voxel grid. To get even smoother results, we model spheroids composed of supersampled voxels around each point in the point cloud (Figure 8). The resolution of the voxel grid can be tuned so that the spheroids are large enough to print with a given additive manufacturing technology.

Models with fine or overhanging geometry are challenging to 3D print. High fidelity reconstructions of landscapes are especially challenging to 3D print because plants have complex, fractal branching structures. Since tombs and markers in burial grounds are often engulfed in vegetation, printing these elements can involve many very small, overhanging parts. Many common types of 3D printing such as fused deposition modeling build scaffolded support structures to hold overhanging parts. It can be impractical to remove support structures from models with complex geometry when small parts are entangled in the scaffolding. There are 3D printing technologies, however, such as binder jetting, material jetting, and powder bed fusion that do not print support structures because parts are built in a bed of raw material. We used selective laser sintering with a polyamide and aluminum powder to print burial ground scenes with strong yet flexible parts, built without support structures (Figure 12).

Figure 7: Neural rendering versus point cloud

Figure 8: Volumetric modeling

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3 Burial Grounds

- | | | |
|-----------------------------------|--------------------------------------|----------------------------------|
| 1. Kelson | 17. Christ Baptist Church | 33. Old Folks Home |
| 2. Mt. Zion Riverlake | 18. Allendale | 34. Sweet Olive |
| 3. Yattan | 19. Shiloh Baptist | 35. Lutheran Benevolent Society |
| 4. Alma | 20. Barrowza | 36. Little Misery |
| 5. Highland | 21. St. Catherine | 37. Morley |
| 6. Old Alford | 22. Poplar Grove | 38. Union Baptist |
| 7. Alford | 23. Anchorage | 39. Antioch Baptist |
| 8. Old St. Peter Baptist Church | 24. Westover | 40. Rock Zion Baptist Church |
| 9. St. Peter Baptist | 25. Homestead | 41. Israelite Baptist Church |
| 10. Greater Mount Calvary Baptist | 26. Second Baptist Church | 42. Red Eye |
| 11. Ashland | 27. Silvery | 43. Old Rock Zion Baptist Church |
| 12. Chamberlin | 28. Lady of Knight | 44. Marks |
| 13. Orange Grove | 29. White Family | 45. Australia |
| 14. Mulatto Bend | 30. United Benevolent Society | 46. Nazarene Baptist Church |
| 15. Belle Vale | 31. Wilbert | 47. Mount Olive |
| 16. Allendale-Hamilton | 32. Scott United Methodist | |

3.1 Alford

Location: West Baton Rouge Parish
Date: 2023-2024
Media: 2 lidar point clouds
51 neural renderings
22 ambisonic recordings
Tech: DJI Matrice 300 RTK with L1 Lidar
Nikon D5600 & Canon EOS 5DS R
Nerfacto Huge & Splatfacto Big
Zoom H3-VR & Tascam DR-70D

Figure 9: Drone lidar, Alford Cemetery, 2024

Figure 10: Mel-scaled spectrogram, Alford Cemetery, 2024

Figure 11: Point clouds, Alford Cemetery, 2025

Figure 12: 3D Prints, Alford Cemetery, 2025

3.2 Alma

Location: Pointe Coupee Parish
Date: 2024
Media: 1 lidar point clouds
14 ambisonic recordings
DJI Matrice 300 RTK with L1 Lidar
Tech: Zoom H3-VR & Tascam DR-70D

Figure 13: Drone lidar, Alma Cemetery, 2024

Figure 14: Mel-scaled spectrogram, Alma Cemetery, 2024

3.3 Ashland

Location: West Baton Rouge Parish
Date: 2024
Media: 1 lidar point clouds
2 ambisonic recordings
DJI Matrice 300 RTK with L1 Lidar
Tech: Zoom H3-VR

Figure 15: Drone lidar, Ashland Cemetery, 2024

Figure 16: Mel-scaled spectrogram, Ashland Cemetery, 2024

3.4 Chamberlin

Location: West Baton Rouge Parish
Date: 2024
Media: 1 lidar point clouds
3 ambisonic recordings
DJI Matrice 300 RTK with L1 Lidar
Tech: Zoom H3-VR & Tascam DR-70D

Figure 17: Drone lidar, Chamberlin Cemetery, 2024

Figure 18: Mel-scaled spectrogram, Chamberlin Cemetery, 2024

3.5 Lady of Knight

Location: West Baton Rouge Parish
Date: 2024
Media: 1 lidar point clouds
1 ambisonic recording
Tech: DJI Matrice 300 RTK with L1 Lidar
Zoom H3-VR

Figure 19: Drone lidar, Lady of Knight Cemetery, 2024

Figure 20: Mel-scaled spectrogram, Lady of Knight Cemetery, 2024

3.6 Mulatto Bend

Location: West Baton Rouge Parish
Date: 2024
Media: 1 point cloud
3 ambisonic recordings
Tech: DJI Matrice 300 RTK with L1 Lidar
Zoom H3-VR

Figure 21: Drone lidar, Mulatto Bend Cemetery, 2024

Figure 22: Mel-scaled spectrogram, Mulatto Bend Cemetery, 2024

3.7 Orange Grove

Location: West Baton Rouge Parish
Date: 2024
Media: 1 point cloud
9 ambisonic recordings
Tech: DJI Matrice 300 RTK with L1 Lidar
Zoom H3-VR & Tascam DR-70D

Figure 23: Drone lidar, Orange Grove Cemetery, 2024

Figure 24: Mel-scaled spectrogram, Orange Grove Cemetery, 2024

3.8 Mt. Zion Riverlake

Location: Pointe Coupee Parish
Date: 2024
Media: 1 point cloud
Tech: DJI Matrice 300 RTK with L1 Lidar

Figure 25: Drone lidar, Mt. Zion Riverlake Cemetery, 2024

3.9 Silvery

Location: West Baton Rouge Parish
Date: 2024
Media: 1 point cloud
Tech: DJI Matrice 300 RTK with L1 Lidar

Figure 26: Drone lidar, Silvery Cemetery, 2024

3.10 St. Catherine

Location: West Baton Rouge Parish
Date: 2024
Media: 1 point cloud
Tech: DJI Matrice 300 RTK with L1 Lidar

Figure 27: Drone lidar, St. Catherine Cemetery, 2024

3.11 United Benevolent Society

Location: West Baton Rouge Parish
Date: 2024
Media: 1 point cloud
1 ambisonic recording
Tech: DJI Matrice 300 RTK with L1 Lidar
Zoom H3-VR

Figure 28: Drone lidar, United Benevolent Society Cemetery, 2024

Figure 29: Mel-scaled spectrogram, United Benevolent Society Cemetery, 2024

4 Dataset

- [22] Brendan Harmon, Nicholas Serrano, Annicia Streete, Roman Carlos, Brooks Joseph, Chapman Cecil, Robertson Caroline, Baos Christos, and Hargis Graham. *African American Burial Grounds in the Louisiana River Parishes*. Version 1.0.0. License: Creative Commons Zero. Zenodo, 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17613647.

5 Papers

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6 Presentations

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7 Poster

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8 Exhibitions

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